

Comparative study of right atrial versus bi-atrial cardioneuroablation of asystolic reflex syncope verified by implantable loop recorder

Acronym: *ILR - CNA*

Short title: Implantable loop recorder and cardioneuroablation

Clinical Investigation Plan

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Gruppo Italiano Multidisciplinare per lo Studio della Sincope

Steering Committee	List of the PIs from all participating centres will be updated
Sponsor	Independent investigator-initiated study supported by the non-profit scientific organizations Gruppo Italiano Multidisciplinare per lo Studio della Sincope (GIMSI), Rimini, Italy
Independent expert(s)	TBD

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Background

Challenges in obtaining reliable follow-up

Cardioneuroablation (CNA) therapy for reflex asystolic syncope is becoming more popular (1). However, there is only one small randomized controlled trial (2) and a few meta-analyses of small to moderate observational studies available (3)(4). Assessing CNA's clinical efficacy is challenging due to symptom variability, intermittent presentation, complex pathophysiology, and diverse treatment options. The difficulty of obtaining precise follow-up data in patients with intermittent symptoms is well known. In two meta-analyses of observational studies (3,4), that virtually cover all the existing literature, the recurrence rate of syncope widely ranged from 0% in some studies to up to 30% in others. Syncope recurrence was as high as 33% at 1 year of follow-up in a multicentre study (5). Such variability indicates a lack of standardized follow-up assessment, beyond differences in expertise or technique. Finally, some expectation bias for both patients and physicians is likely (6,7,8).

Importance of continuous ECG monitoring by means on implantable loop recorder (ILR)

More objective monitoring can be achieved with ILR. In the recent Italian CNA study (9), 28 patients with severe, asystolic reflex syncope identified by ILR or tilt testing underwent right atrial CNA and were subsequently monitored using ILR. The primary endpoint was the frequency of asystolic episodes per month detected through ILR monitoring before and after ablation. The burden of asystolic episodes significantly reduced from 0.89 episodes per month before CNA to 0.11 episodes per month after CNA, with a relative risk reduction (RRR) of 0.12, $p=0.0001$. Monthly assessment of heart rate (HR) and of heart rate variability (HRV) was conducted before and after ablation up to 15 months. The median heart rate recorded by ILR increased from 75 bpm (IQR: 72-79) before ablation to 83 bpm (IQR: 78-85) after ablation, lasting up to 9 months post-procedure. ILR monitoring has been used only seldom with bi-atrial CNA in few case reports (11,12). Thus, no comparison between right versus bi-atrial ablation is available.

Gap in knowledge

The best method of CNA is debated, with no studies comparing right versus bi-atrial ablation. An acute randomized study found bi-atrial ablation necessary for a complete effect (10), while right atrial ablation showed less adverse events during follow-up (9). In a meta-analysis (4), recurrence of syncope was observed in 4.4% of 489 patients with bi-atrial ablation and in 15.8% of 72 patients with right atrial ablation. A similar 15.6% recurrence rate at one year was observed in the Italian CNA study (9)

Aim of the study

Aim of the study is to verify the efficacy of CNA on reduction of reflex asystolic pauses documented by continuous monitoring by means of ILR in patients undergoing right atrial versus bi-atrial ablation (*ILR – CNA study*).

Study design

ILR – CNA study is an observational in which the results of CNA performed in centres that, in their current practice, are utilizing the method of right atrial ablation alone is compared with the results of CNA performed in centres that, in their current practice, are utilizing the method of bi-atrial ablation. This pragmatic approach allows for maintaining usual clinical practices, enrolling consecutive patients without specific exclusion criteria, ensuring enhanced generalizability of findings and low costs (13).

The study is an investigator-initiated independent observational clinical trial, coordinated by the non-profit organization Gruppo Italiano Multidisciplinare per lo Studio della Sincope (GIMSI), Rimini, Italy. In particular, GIMSI Association will supply the ILR LuxDx[®] device and its remote monitoring system Latitude[®]. GIMSI will make the devices necessary for the study available to participating centres. These features are necessary to collect uniform data from the patients and obtaining a standardized high-quality ECG follow-up of the primary endpoint of the study.

The study design is summarized in the **Figure 1**. In accordance with a recent EHRA consensus document (14), the screening of suitable candidates includes detailed history and physical examination and an accurate phenotyping that includes active standing test, 24-hour ambulatory blood pressure monitoring (ABPM), tilt testing and carotid sinus massage.

Eligible patients receive the implantation of a LuxDx[®] ILR and are monitored for one month by means of the Latitude Clarity data management system of the device. The usual practice of the centres is unchanged. According to their usual practice, the centres are assigned to right atrial ablation group or to bi-atrial ablation group. The patients receive a right atrial procedure or a biatrial procedure accordingly. As per pragmatic design, cross-over are permitted according to investigator judgment. The ablation methods and techniques are left to investigator's decision. They are reported in the CRF. After the ablation procedure, the patients are monitored continuously by the Latitude Clarity data management system of the device for 12 months. See **Table 1**

Study design

Figure 1. study design.

Table 1. Tests and data collection

ILR monitoring	Enrolment	Before CNA (M-1)	M 3	M 6	M 9	M 12
Structured history	X					
Active standing test	X					
Prolonged ECG monitoring	X					
24-hour ambulatory BP monitoring	X					
Tilt testing	X					
Carotid sinus massage	X					
Data from ILR monitoring		Continuous				
Asystolic syncopes		X	X	X	X	X
Non-asystolic syncopes		X	X	X	X	X
Adverse events			X	X	X	X

Inclusion Criteria:

- Age 18 to 60 years
- Clinical diagnosis of reflex syncope as per class I criteria of the ESC guidelines
- History of recurrent severe syncopes (≥ 2 in the last year or ≥ 3 in the last 2 years), significantly affecting the quality of life, nonresponding to lifestyle measures.
- Documentation by means of prolonged ECG monitoring of an asystolic pause >6 sec or of an asystolic syncope >3 sec and/or an asystolic syncope induced during tilt testing (Vasis 2B form).

Exclusion Criteria:

- Intrinsic sinus dysfunction or atrioventricular node disease.
- Constitutional hypotension and orthostatic intolerance syndromes
- Overt structural heart disease
- Alternative diagnoses of syncope
- Pregnancy or breastfeeding

Endpoints

- The primary endpoint is the frequency of asystolic episodes >3 sec per month detected through ILR monitoring before and after ablation.
- The secondary endpoints are: 1) the freedom from ablation-related complications and from pacemaker implantation during the follow-up period; 2) the burden of syncopal episodes before and after ablation; 3) the time to first asystolic pause >3 sec and to first syncope recurrence, and 3) the pattern of heart rate (HR) and heart rate variability (HRV) detected by ILR after ablation.

Ablation procedures

The ablation methods and techniques are left to investigator's decision. They are reported in the CRF as listed in the **Table 2**.

Table 2. Ablation methods and techniques (according to the EHRA position paper classification (15))

Target ganglia (multiple choices are permitted)	Method of identification (multiple choices are permitted)	Procedural measures before and after CNA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RSGP • RIGP • PLMGP • LSGP • LIGP • MTGP • Other sites 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-frequency stimulation • Electrogram-based approach • Anatomically-guided (EP mapping) • Anatomically-guided (CT or MRI imaging) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sinus rate (avg 10 beats) • cSNRT • AH interval • AV node Wenckebach point • Atropine test (0.04 mg per Kg i.v.)

Follow-up

ILR functions are programmed as default except for pause duration 3 sec daytime and nighttime. The ECG data are collected by the LATITUDE Electronic Medical Record (EMR) system integration feature and then reported in the electronic CRF. EMR is programmed "Enabled". Data cover one month before the CNA and the whole duration of follow-up. HR recorded by ILR is monitored continuously. The graphical trend viewable on the Health tab of the Patient Detail page is printed as PDF and stored in the electronic CRF. Asystolic episodes >3 sec are monitored continuously by ILR throughout the study and are reported in the CRF. These include, date (day/hour/min), duration and type (Issue classification).

Syncopal recurrences and complications post-CNA are assessed quarterly by the investigators (**Table 1**).

Adverse events are assessed by a formal questionnaire that uses the same classification used by Kulakowski et al (15) (**Table 3**)

Table 3. Adverse events during the follow-up (according to the Kulakowski classification (16))

Adverse event
Redo CNA
Pacemaker implantation
Transient dyspnoea
Chronic chest pain
Decreased exercise capacity
Transient palpitations (<3 months)
Persistent palpitations

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis

The burden of asystolic episodes (primary endpoint) will be calculated as number of asystolic episodes >3 sec per month. The burden in the right atrial ablation group will be compared with the burden in the bi-atrial ablation group and will be compared by mean of the t test or the non-parametric Mann-Whitney test as appropriate. The burden of syncopal episodes (secondary endpoint) will be calculated with the same method. Kaplan-Meier estimate will be used to calculate the times to first asystolic pause and to first syncopal recurrence. Log rank test will be used to compare these estimates between the two groups. The mean HR will be compared by means of the T test between groups

Sample size estimation

In absence of ILR data in the bi-atrial group, the sample calculation is based on surrogate findings. In the Piotrowski RCT (10), the acute endpoint of full vagal ablation was achieved in 35% of right atrial group versus 80% of left atrial group. Assuming 50% reduction of asystole burden in bi-atrial group compared with right atrial group, 44 patients (22 per group) are needed to have 90% probability to achieve a two-sided significance level of 0.05. With an attrition of 10%, **50 patients (25 per group)** are needed to show a superiority of bi-atrial ablation.

Ad-interim analysis

An ad-interim analysis is performed when 80% of patients per arm have performed CNA procedure.

Timeline

Recruitment starts on third quarter 2025 and ends in December 2026. Follow-up ends in December 2027.

Study centres: a maximum of 10 centres routinely performing right ablation and 10 centres routinely performing bi-atrial ablation are involved in the study

Provisional list of centres (to be updated):

Bi-atrial ablation	Right-atrial ablation
IRCCS Auxologico, Milano	Ospedale Clinico Casilino, Roma
Ospedale Università Molinette, Torino	Ospedale Vanvitelli, Napoli

IRCCS Humanitas, Rozzano	Ospedale Centrale, Bolzano
Ospedale Maria Cecilia, Cotignola	Ospedali del Tigullio, Lavagna
Ospedale S. Andrea, Vercelli	Arcispedale S Maria Nuova, Reggio Emilia
Centro Cardiologico Monzino, Milano	Ospedale S. Giuseppe, Empoli
Università delle Marche, Ancona	Ospedale S. Maria Annunziata, Bagno a Ripoli, Firenze
Ospedale CG Mazzoni, Ascoli Piceno	
Azienda Ospedaliero Universitaria Careggi, Firenze	

Safety Reporting

Adverse events (AEs)

Adverse events are defined as any undesirable experience occurring to a participant during the study, whether or not considered related to the trial procedure. All adverse events reported spontaneously by the participant or observed by the investigator, or his staff will be recorded.

Serious adverse events (SAEs)

A serious adverse event is any untoward medical occurrence or effect that :

- results in death;
- is life threatening (at the time of the event);
- requires hospitalisation or prolongation of existing inpatients' hospitalisation;
- results in persistent or significant disability or incapacity;
- is a congenital anomaly or birth defect; or
- any other important medical event that did not result in any of the outcomes listed above due to medical or surgical intervention but could have been based upon appropriate judgement by the investigator.
- An elective hospital admission will not be considered as a serious adverse event.

The investigator will report all SAEs to the project leader without undue delay after obtaining knowledge of the events. The project leader will report the SAEs to the accredited EC that approved the protocol, within 7 days of first knowledge for SAEs that result in death or are life threatening followed by a period of maximum of 8 days to complete the initial preliminary report. All other SAEs will be reported within a period of maximum 15 days after the project leader has first knowledge of serious adverse events.

AEs and SAEs related to the ablation:

The causality of AE's and SAE's in relation to the procedure will be determined by the investigator and it will be classified as:

- AE/SAE is clearly related to the procedure if:

- Follows a reasonable temporal sequence from undergoing the treatment.
- Follows a known response pattern to undergoing the treatment (if response pattern is previously known).
- No other reasonable cause is present.

- AE/SAE is probably related to the procedure if:

- Follows a reasonable temporal sequence from undergoing the treatment, and plausible reasons point to a causal relation undergoing the treatment.

- AE/SAE is possibly related to the procedure if:

- Follows a reasonable temporal sequence from undergoing the treatment.
- The AE may equally be explained by the study subject's clinically state, environmental or toxic factors, or concomitant therapy administered to the study subject.
- The relationship between the treatment and AE/SAE may also be clinically plausible.

- AE/SAE is not related to the procedure if:

- May or may not follow a reasonable temporal sequence from administration of the treatment
- It is biologically implausible and does not follow known response pattern to the treatment (if response pattern is previously known)
- Can be explained by the known characteristics of the subject's clinical state or other modes of therapy administered to the subject.

- AE/SAE is not assessable if:

- The causal relationship between the trial procedure and the AE/SAE cannot be judged within the reasonable known scientific knowledge.

8.3. Follow-up of Adverse Events

All AEs will be followed until they have abated, or until a stable situation has been reached. Depending on the event, follow up may require additional tests or medical procedures as indicated, and/or referral to the general physician or a medical specialist.

Ethical Considerations

Regulation statement

This trial will be conducted in accordance with the latest version of the Declaration of Helsinki, ICH Guidelines for Good Clinical Practice (GCP), the Medical Research Involving Human Subjects Act (WMO) and other relevant Italian and international laws, regulations and codes of conduct. To avoid publication bias and duplicate studies, the trial will be registered on <http://clinicaltrials.gov>.

Informed Consent Process

The investigator ensures patients receive full and adequate oral and written information about the study's aim, nature, possible risks, and benefits. Patients are notified of voluntary participation and their freedom to withdraw without consequences. They are informed of an independent expert available for questions. Patients are given sufficient time to consider information and ask questions. If the patient understands and wishes to participate, they sign the informed consent form. The signed and dated form is obtained and filed before any study procedure. The original is stored at the research site, with a copy given to the patient. At the visit where informed consent is acquired, baseline characteristics relevant to the study will also be collected.

Compensation for injury

The sponsor has a liability insurance which is in accordance with article 7 of the WMO. The sponsor (also) has an insurance which is in accordance with the legal requirements in Italy (Article 7 WMO). This insurance provides cover for damage to research participants through injury or death caused by the study. The insurance applies to the damage that becomes apparent during the study or within 4 years after the end of the study.

Incentives:

Patients will not receive any financial incentives for participating in the study.

Structured Risk Analysis

Potential issues of concern

This trial will execute medical procedures that are already integrated into routine clinical care. All eligible patients have severely symptomatic reflex syncope that is unsuitable for non-invasive care.

Procedural Risks

Performing ganglia ablation naturally inherent a well-documented risk. These risks include (but are not limited to) bleeding, vascular complications, cardiac perforation, cardiac tamponade, stroke,

infection and lead related complications. To minimize these risks, the procedures will be performed by experienced electrophysiologists following standardized protocols and using appropriate precautions.

Anesthesia-related Risks:

The standard practice of ganglia ablation mandate patient sedation and local anesthesia usage for optimal patient comfort and to facilitate the procedure execution. This is a standard clinical practice, and no additional action will be performed for the sole purpose of the trial. There are potential risks associated with anesthesia administration, including allergic reactions, respiratory complications, and cardiovascular instability. Anesthesia will be administered by qualified physician who will carefully monitor patients throughout the procedure to minimize any adverse events.

Adverse Events

There is a possibility of experiencing adverse events related to the interventions or study procedures. Possible complications of this trial procedure include bleeding, vascular complications, cardiac perforation, pneumothorax, TIA/stroke, cardiac tamponade, AV node block. Although the risks are generally low, they can vary depending on individual factors and the procedure itself. Adverse events will be closely monitored, documented, and reported in accordance with predefined protocols.

Mitigation Strategies

To mitigate the potential risks associated with the study, several strategies will be implemented:

- Rigorous participant screening and selection based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- Detailed informed consent process, ensuring participants' understanding of potential risks and benefits.
- Implementation of standardized protocols for interventions, anesthesia, and AE management.
- Continuous training of study personnel involved in the procedures and participant care.

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